

Regression is a tool to Measure the Working Capital Performance - Impact on Profitability of Banks: A Case Study of SBI & HDFC Bank Ltd.

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Article Info

Volume 83

Page Number: 24919- 24933

Publication Issue:

March - April 2020

Abstract

Profitability is the financial measure of firm's ability to earn profit. It can be measured through Working Capital Performance, such as current assets and current liabilities. It is important for banks to have efficient working capital practices as a portion of funds is parked to meet short term financial obligations to stakeholders of banks and ability to continue its operations. The idea of this paper is to examine the working capital impact over the profitability used a statistical tool with regression analysis to measure the financial performance of the SBI and HDFC top ranked two banks in India. These banks, shows a tremendous growth over the year. Data for these two banks were collected for five years from 2013-14 to 2018-19 from secondary sources and analyzed. It was found out that the relationship between working capital performance with profitability ratios consisting of gross profit ratio, net profit ratio, operating profit ratio, return on equity, return on capital employed and earnings per share of the two select banks. It also studies the relationship between these variables using regressions, z- test, Correlation and used t- test for hypothesis testing. Findings of this study all profitability components are uniformly influenced the working capital performance of SBI and HDFC.

Article History

Article Received: 24 July 2019

Revised: 12 September 2019

Accepted: 15 February 2020

Publication: 30 April 2020

Keywords; Working Capital management, Profitability, Regression Analysis, Return on Equity, Return on Capital Employed, EPS, etc.

I. INTRODUCTION

Every business needs funds for two purposes for its establishment and to carry out its day to day operations. Working capital refers to that part of the firm's capital which is required for financing short term or current assets such as cash, bank, marketable securities, bills, receivables, debtors and inventories. Working capital is the required amount of funds needed to cover the cost of operating the enterprise. Working capital refers to the funds invested in current assets i.e. investment in stocks, sundry debtors, cash and other current assets. Current assets are essential to use fixed assets profitably. For example a machine cannot be used without raw material. Thus it is obvious

that certain amount of funds is always tied up in raw materials and work in progress, finished goods. However, the business also enjoys credit facilities from its suppliers who may supply raw materials on credit and the firm may not pay immediately all expenses. Therefore, certain amount of funds is automatically available to finance the current assets requirements. However, the requirements for current assets are usually greater than the amount of funds payable through current liabilities. In other words, current assets are to be kept at a higher level than the current liabilities. The object of Working capital management is to deal with the current assets and current liabilities of the firm in such a way that a satisfactory level of Working capital is maintained. Working capital is the difference between the

inflow and out flow of funds .Working capital is also known as working or circulating capital or short term capital.

I. LITERATURE REVIEW

The main of the review of literature is a systematic analysis of the previous studies on the working capital management to provide the background and develop a link to the present study.

Guthmann&Dougall (1948) who defined working capital as excess of current assets over current liabilities.

Park &Gladson (1963) Identified working capital as the excess of current assets of a business. Over current items owed to employees i.e. salaries and wages Payable, accounts payable, taxes owed to government.

Gole (1959) Opinion that concept of working capital, as has been commonly understood by the accountants, is more particularly considered as net working capital to distinguish it from gross working capital.

II. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- i. To examine the nature of relationship between Working Capital and Profitability of SBI and HDFC during the period from 2014 to 2019.
- ii. To discover the impact of Working Capital performance on Profitability of SBI and HDFC during the period from 2014 to 2019.

III. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

The following hypotheses are formulated for the study;

H₁: There is no significance relationship between Working Capital and Gross Profit.

H₂:There is a no significance relationship between Working Capital and Net Profit.

H₃: There is no significance relationship between Working Capital and Operating Profit.

H₄:There is no significance relationship between Working Capital and Return on Capital Employed.

H₅: There is no significance relationship between Working Capital and Return on Equity.

H₆: There is no significance relationship between Working Capital and Earnings per Share.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology of the present study is outlined below.

The design of the present study is analytical in nature to covers the period of five years from 2014-15 to 2018-2019. The data which is required for the analysis and that could accomplish our objectives that have been collected mainly from two sources, viz 1) primary and 2) secondary data.

Primary data was collected from the bank officials and accounts departments through interviews and discussions regarding different aspects of the SBI and HDFC.Secondary data obtained from the audited balance sheets and profit & loss accounts, operational reports and also the annual reports of SBI and HDFC.

For analyzing the data statistical techniques have been used such as arithmetic mean, standard deviation, Co-variance, Regression and F-test are used for this study. For these statistical measures are calculated by using a tool SPSS soft ware.

V. CONCEPTUAL FRAME WORK

Working Capital Ratio: Book value of Working Capital divided by book value of Total Assets

VI. Working Capital

VII. Working Capital Ratio = $\frac{\text{Working Capital}}{\text{Total Assets}}$

VIII. **Independent variables of Profitability key components:**

IX. The independent variables of profitability like gross profit ratio, net profit ratio, operating profit ratio, return on capital employed, return on net worth and earnings per share are used as the determinants to analyze the dependent variable i.e...., the working capital ratio. Several independent variables are taken with the view to assess the profitability performance on Working Capital of two select banks. The independent variables are:

No.			
1	Gross Profit Ratio	Gross Profit to Sales	(Gross Profit/Sales) *100
2	Net Profit Ratio	Net Profit to Sales	(Net Profit/Sales) *100
3	Operating Profit Ratio	Operating Profit to Sales	(Operating Profit/ Sales) *100
4	Return on Capital Employed	EBIT to Capital Employed	(EBIT/Capital Employed) *100
5	Return on Equity	PAT to Equity	(PAT/Equity) *100
6	Earnings per Share	PAT to No. of Equity Shares	(PAT/Equity Shares) *100
Source: Predictions			

List of Independent Variables

S.	Ratio	Relationship	Proxy
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Table-1: Statement of Working Capital Ratio

Year	SBI				HDFC			
	Working Capital	Total Assets	WC Ratio (%)	Trend	Working Capital	Total Assets	WC Ratio (%)	Trend
2014-15	13,82,822	18,73,910	73.79	-	4,03,256	5,58,019	72.22	-
2015-16	16,12,300	21,98,341	73.34	99.39	5,04,892	7,04,071	71.59	99.12
2016-17	17,41,823	25,50,731	68.24	92.48	5,89,041	8,07,131	72.98	101.05
2017-18	21,86,635	32,87,614	66.50	90.12	7,72,363	10,18,171	75.83	104.99
2018-19	25,29,097	35,35,317	71.54	96.95	8,94,814	11,89,432	75.19	104.11
Mean	18,90,535	26,89,183	70.68	94.74	6,32,873	8,55,365	73.56	102.32
SD	4,61,719	7,06,899	3.19	4.20	1,99,433	2,50,867	1.86	2.71
Co-Variance	24.42	26.28	4.51	4.43	31.51	29.32	2.53	2.65

Source: Annual Reports of SBI and HDFC, * Trend base year 2014-15

Working Capital Ratio: It can be seen from the Table-1, The Working Capital performance of the SBI and HDFC. Average ratio and trend of this ratio of SBI is 70.68 and 94.74 percent. It is observed Spread is 3.19 and consistence for last five years of this ratio is 4.41 percent. Trend spread is 2.71 times and consistence rate is 4.43 percent.

On the other hand, HDFC; average and average trend rate of working capital ratio is 73.56 and 102.32 percent. Spread is only 1.86 times and its consistency is 2.53 percent. Averaged trend rate of working ratio is 2.71 times and growth consistence is 2.65 percent. Comparatively, it is observed that the working capital performance of HDFC was better than SBI during the study

period. It is the quantity of operational modes the item allows. Regularly, a industrial item permits just not exactly a couple of thousand methods of activity with various blends of its machine settings. Be that as it may, software bundles

permit a large number of operational conceivable outcomes. Thus, guaranteeing of all these operational conceivable outcomes accurately is a noteworthy test to the software industry.

Year	SBI				HDFC			
	Gross Profit	Turnover	GPR (%)	Trend	Gross Profit	Turnover	GRR (%)	Trend
2014-15	77,591	1,74,973	44.25	-	31,392	57,466	54.38	-
2015-16	85,040	1,91,844	44.50	101.69	38,343	70,973	53.52	98.42
2016-17	97,321	2,10,979	45.97	103.88	45,435	81,602	55.55	102.15
2017-18	1,19,454	2,65,100	44.90	101.47	55,316	95,462	57.89	106.45
2018-19	1,25,124	2,79,644	44.80	101.24	65,869	1,16,598	56.00	102.98
Mean	1,00,906	2,24,508	44.88	102.07	47,271	84,420	55.47	102.50
SD	20,849	45,802	0.66	1.22	13,655	22,763	1.67	3.29
Co-Variance	20.67	20.40	1.47	1.19	28.88	26.96	2.99	3.21

Source: Annual Reports of SBI and HDFC, * Trend base year 2014-15

Gross Profit Ratio: It can be seen from the Table-2, The Gross Profitability performance of the SBI and HDFC. Average ratio and trend of this ratio of SBI is 44.88 and 102.07 percent. It can be seen spread is 0.66 times and consistence for last five years of this ratio is 1.47 percent. Its trend spread is 1.22 times and its consistence is 1.19 percent.

On the other hand, HDFC; average and average trend rate of Gross Profit ratio is 55.47 and 102.50 percent. Spread is only 1.67 times and its consistency is 2.99 percent. Trend spread of gross profit ratio is 3.29 times and its consistency is 3.21 percent. Comparatively, it is observed that the gross profit performance; HDFC is better and risk

Year	SBI				HDFC			
	Net Profit	Turnover	NPR (%)	Trend	Net Profit	Turnover	NPR (%)	Trend
2014-15	13,102	1,74,973	7.47	-	10,216	57,466	17.54	-
2015-16	9,951	1,91,844	4.71	63.05	12,296	70,973	16.90	96.35
2016-17	10,484	2,10,979	4.76	63.72	14,550	81,602	17.28	98.52
2017-18	-6,547	2,65,100	-2.26	-30.25	17,487	95,462	17.89	101.99
2018-19	862	2,79,644	0.31	4.15	21,078	1,16,598	18.10	103.19
Mean	5570	2,24,508	2.99	25.17	15,125	84,420	17.54	100.01
SD	8,201	45,802	3.90	46.31	4285	22,763	0.47	3.143
Co-Variance	147.23	20.40	130.43	180.12	28.33	26.96	2.68	3.14

Source: Annual Reports of SBI and HDFC, * Trend base year 2014-15

and consistency point of view SBI is better.

Net Profit Ratio: It can be seen from the Table-3, The Net Profitability performance of the SBI and HDFC. Average ratio and trend of this ratio of SBI is 2.55 and 25.177 percent. It is found high spread i.e. 3.99 times and consistence for last five years of this ratio is 130.43 percent. Its trend spread is 46.31 times and consistence rate is 180.12 percent.

On the other hand, HDFC; average and average trend rate of Net Profit ratio is 17.54 and 100.01

percent. Spread is only 0.47 times and its consistency is 2.68 percent. Trend percent of net profit ratio is 3.143 times and consistence rate is 3.14 percent. Comparatively, it is observed that the net profit performance; HDFC has high profitability and lower risk than the SBI.

Operating Profit Ratio: It can be seen from the Table-4, The Operating Profitability performance of the SBI and HDFC. Average ratio and trend of this ratio of SBI is 77.36 and 99.44 percent.

Table-4: Statement of Operating Profit Ratio

Year	SBI				HDFC			
	Operating Profit	Turnover	OPR (%)	Trend	Operating Profit	Turnover	OPR (%)	Trend
2014-15	1,36,919	1,74,973	77.71	-	43,478	57,466	75.44	-
2015-16	1,49,762	1,91,844	78.12	100.53	53,993	70,973	74.64	98.94
2016-17	1,64,506	2,10,979	78.09	100.49	61,899	81,602	76.54	101.46
2017-18	2,05,157	2,65,100	77.36	99.55	73,146	95,462	76.84	101.85
2018-19	2,09,956	2,79,644	75.52	97.18	90,922	1,16,598	78.45	103.99
Mean	1,73,260	2,24,508	77.36	99.44	64,688	84,420	76.38	101.56
SD	32,838	45,802	1.07	1.57	18,246	22,763	1.45	2.07
Co-Variance	18.95	20.40	1.38	1.58	28.21	26.96	1.89	2.04

Source: Annual Reports of SBI and HDFC, * Trend base year 2014-15

Observed spread i.e. 1.07 times and consistence for last five years of this ratio is 1.38 percent. Its trend spread is 1.57 times and consistence rate is 1.58 percent.

On the other hand, HDFC; average and average trend rate of operating profit ratio is 76.38 and

101.56 percent. Spread is 1.45 times and its consistency is 1.89 percent. Trend percent of operating profit ratio is 2.07 times and consistence rate is 2.07 percent. Comparatively, it is observed that the operating profit performance point of view SBI is better than the HDFC.

Table-5: Statement of Return on Capital Employed

Year	SBI				HDFC			
	PBIT	Capital Employed	ROCE (%)	Trend	PBIT	Capital Employed	ROCE (%)	Trend
2014-15	39,538	18,73,910	2.08	-	17,404	5,58,019	3.04	-
2015-16	43,258	21,98,341	1.95	93.75	21,363	7,04,071	2.98	98.02
2016-17	50,848	25,50,731	2.00	96.15	25,733	8,07,131	3.09	101.64
2017-18	59,058	32,87,614	1.79	86.06	32,625	10,18,171	3.14	103.29
2018-19	55,432	35,35,317	1.55	75.52	39,750	11,89,432	3.28	107.89
Mean	49,627	26,89,182	1.87	87.87	27,375	8,55,365	3.11	102.71
SD	8,162	7,06,899	0.21	9.29	8,929	2,50,867	0.11	4.09
Co-Variance	16.45	26.28	11.22	10.57	32.62	29.33	3.54	3.98

Source: Annual Reports of SBI and HDFC, * Trend base year 2014-15

Return on Capital Employed: – It can be seen from the Table-5, The Return on Capital Employed performance of the SBI and HDFC. Average ratio and trend of this ratio of SBI is 1.87 and 87.87 percent. Observed low spread i.e. 0.21 times and consistence for last five years of this ratio is 11.22 percent. Its trend spread is 9.29 times and consistence rate is 10.57 percent.

On the other hand, HDFC; average and average trend rate of ROCE is 3.11 and 102.71 percent. Spread is 0.11 times and its consistency is 3.54

percent. Trend percent of return on capital employed ratio is 4.09 times and consistence rate is 3.98 percent. Comparatively, it is observed that HDFC is better performance with ROCE than SBI. It indicated that HDFC has high return on capital employed.

Return on Equity: It can be seen from the Table-6, The Return on Equity performance of the SBI and HDFC. Average ratio and trend of this ratio of SBI is 4.20 and 26.77 percent.

Table-6: Statement of Return on Equity

Year	SBI				HDFC			
	PAT	Equity	ROE (%)	Trend	PAT	Equity	ROE (%)	Trend
2014-15	13,102	1,28,438	10.15	-	10,216	62,009	16.13	-
2015-16	9,951	1,44,274	7.89	77.73	12,296	72,678	16.67	103.35
2016-17	10,484	1,88,286	5.32	52.41	14,550	89,462	17.73	109.92
2017-18	-6,517	2,19,129	-2.74	-26.99	17,487	1,06,295	16.03	99.38
2018-19	882	2,20,914	0.40	3.94	21,078	1,49,206	14.09	87.35
Mean	5,580	1,80,208	4.20	26.77	15,125	95,930	16.13	100
SD	8,187	42,451	5.31	47.14	4,285	34,201	1.32	9.49
Co-Variance	146.72	23.55	126.43	176.06	28.33	35.65	8.18	9.49

Source: Annual Reports of SBI and HDFC, * Trend base year 2014-15

Observed low spread i.e. 5.31 times and high consistence for last five years of this ratio is 126.43 percent. Its trend spread is 47.14 times and high consistence rate is 176.06 percent.

On the other hand, HDFC; average and average trend rate of ROE is 16.13 and 100 percent.

Spread is 1.32 times and its consistency is 8.18 percent. Trend percent of return on equity ratio is 9.49 times and consistence rate is 9.49 percent. Comparatively, it is observed that HDFC is good performance with ROE than SBI. It reflected that HDFC has high return on its equity.

Table-7: Statement of Earnings Per Share

Year	SBI				HDFC			
	Earnings	Holding	EPS(Times)	Trend	Earnings	Holding	EPS (Times)	Trend
2014-15	13,102	2,22,341	16.97	-	10,216	3,99,752	39.13	-
2015-16	9,951	1,23,169	12.39	73.01	12,296	5,74,223	46.70	119.34
2016-17	10,484	1,33,776	12.76	75.19	14,550	8,26,149	56.78	145.10
2017-18	-6,517	-	0	0	17,487	11,78,274	67.38	172.19
2018-19	882	856	0.97	5.72	21,078	16,32,437	77.40	197.80
Mean	5,580	1,44,075	8.62	38.48	15,125	9,22,167	57.48	158.61
SD	8,187	89,967	7.64	41.21	4,285	4,93,273	15.39	33.88

Co-Variance	146.72	62.44	88.63	107.09	28.33	53.49	26.77	21.36
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Source: Annual Reports of SBI and HDFC, * Trend base year 2014-15

Earnings per Share: It can be seen from the Table-7, Earnings per Share performance of the SBI and HDFC. Average ratio and trend of this ratio of SBI is 8.62 and 38.48 percent. Observed spread i.e. 7.64 times and consistence for last five years of this ratio is 88.63 percent. Its trend spread is 41.21 times and high consistence rate is 107.09 percent.

On the other hand, HDFC; average and average trend rate of EPS is 57.48 and 158.61 percent. Spread is 15.39 times and its consistency is 26.77 percent. Trend percent of EPS is 33.88 times and consistence rate is 21.36 percent. Comparatively, it is observed that HDFC is good performance with EPS than SBI. It reflected that HDFC has high returns shared to its shareholders.

X. REGRESSION ANALYSIS

An attempt has made to examine and test the explanatory power of the conventional theoretical

framework of banks specific components of profitability. The Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regressions were run on the date, with Working Capital was dependent variable and the bank profitability factors as the independent variables, those are GPR, NPR, OPR, ROCE, ROE and EPS. Regression analysis was undertaken to find out the relationship between Working Capital and Profitability components of both SBI and HDFC. The F-test, when used for regression analysis, it compares two competing regression models in their ability to “explain” the variance in the dependent variable. Regression Coefficients of Working Capital and Profitability were shown in the Table No.8 to 12.

H1: There is no significance relationship between Working Capital and Gross Profit.

Table 8.1 - Model Summary Between Working Capital and Gross Profit

Model	SBI				HDFC			
	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.68	.471	.294	2.68675	0.93	.876	.835	.75506

Source: Computed

It can be seen from the above Table No.8.1, overall dependence of Working Capital on Gross Profit of SBI and HDFC. The correlation coefficient between WCR and GPR is 0.68, relationship strength is 0.471, adjusted R square 0.294 and its standard error is 2.69 times for SBI. It indicates that 47.1 percent of profitability of

Gross profit influences the Working Capital performance.

On other hand HDFC, correlation coefficient 0.93, relationship strength is 0.876, adjusted R square 0.876 and standard error is 0.755. In overall result 87.6 percent of Gross Profit, which influences the Working Capital performance.

TABLE 8.2- Summary ANOVA Between Working Capital and Gross Profit

Model		SBI					HDFC				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	19.257	1	19.257	2.668	.201	12.112	1	12.112	21.246	.019
	Residual	21.656	3	7.219			1.710	3	.570		
	Total	40.913	4				13.823	4			

Critical value at 5% Level of Significance is 10.13

Source: Computed

It can be seen from the above Table No.8.2, overall dependence of Working Capital on Gross Profit of SBI and HDFC. By comparing F- values with F- critical value of both the banks, it is observed that null hypothesis accepted for SBI

and rejected for HDFC. Further it is concluded that there is no impact of gross profit on working capital performance of SBI, whereas HDFC, there is an impact of gross profit on working capital performance.

TABLE 8.3 - Summary Coefficients Between Working Capital and Gross Profit

SBI					HDFC						
Model		Unstandardize d Coefficients		Standardize d Coefficients	t	Sig.	Unstandardize d Coefficients		Standardize d Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta			B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	220.16	91.53		2.40	.09	15.70	12.55		1.25	.300
	Gross Profit	-3.330	2.039	-.686	1.63	.20	1.043	.226	.936	4.61	.019

Source: Computed.

It can be observed from Table-8.3 indicates Regression unstandardized and standardized coefficients, standard error and standardized betas of Working Capital and its profitability of SBI and HDFC. It can be seen that gross profit is negative co-efficient relation and negative beta with SBI and positive co-efficient relationship and positive beta with HDFC. It is indicated that there is

relationship exists for both the banks. Further, it is concluded that profitability (Gross Profit) has explained the Working Capital Performance of both the banks.

H2: There is no significance relationship between Working Capital and Net Profit.

Table 9.1 - Model Summary Between Working Capital and Net Profit

Model	SBI				HDFC			
	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.678	.459	.279	2.71560	.878	.771	.694	1.02820

Source: Computed

It can be seen from the above Table No.9.1, overall dependence of Working Capital on Net Profit for SBI and HDFC. The correlation coefficient between WCR and NPR is 0.68, relationship strength is 0.279, adjusted R square 0.459 and its standard error is 2.71 times of SBI. It indicates that 45.9 percent of profitability of Net

profit influences the Working Capital performance.

On other hand HDFC, correlation coefficient 0.88, relationship strength is 0.771, adjusted R square 0.694 and standard error is 1.0282. In overall result 77.1 percent of Net Profit, which is influences the Working Capital performance.

TABLE 9.2 - Summary ANOVA Between Working Capital and Net Profit

	SBI					HDFC				
	Sum of	df	Mean	F	Sig.	Sum of	df	Mean	F	Sig.

Model	Squares		Square			Squares		Square			
1	Regression	18.790	1	18.790	2.548	.209	10.651	1	10.651	10.175	.050
	Residual	22.123	3	7.374			3.172	3	1.057		
	Total	40.913	4				13.823	4			

Critical value at 5% Level of Significance is 10.13

Source: Computed

It can be seen from the above Table No.9.2, overall dependence of Working Capital on Net Profit of SBI and HDFC. By comparing F- values with F- critical value of both the banks, it is

observed that null hypothesis accepted for SBI and rejected for HDFC. Further it is concluded that there is no impact of net profit on working capital performance of SBI and HDFC.

TABLE 9.3 - Summary Coefficients Between Working Capital and Net Profit

SBI					HDFC					
Model		Unstandardize d Coefficients		Standardize d Coefficients	t	Sig.	Unstandardize d Coefficients		t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error				Beta	B		
1	(Constant)	69.01	1.601		43.1	.000	13.65	18.879	.723	.522
	Net Profit	.555	.348	.678	1.59	.209	3.415	1.076	.878	3.170

Source:

Computed.

It can be observed from Table-9.3 indicates Regression unstandardized and standardized coefficients, standard error and standardized betas of Working Capital and its profitability of SBI and HDFC. It can be seen that net profit is positive co-efficient relation and positive beta with both SBI and HDFC. It is indicated that there is

relationship exists for both the banks. Further, it is concluded that profitability (Net Profit) has explained the Working Capital Performance of both the banks.

H3: There is no significance relationship between Working Capital and Operating Profit.

Table 10.1 - Model Summary Between Working Capital and Operating Profit

Model	SBI				HDFC			
	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.018	.000	-.333	3.69231	.835	.697	.596	1.18186

Source: Computed

It can be seen from the above Table No.10.1, overall dependence of Working Capital on Operating Profit of SBI and HDFC. The correlation coefficient between WCR and OPR is 0.018, relationship strength is 0.000, and adjusted R square -0.333 and its standard error is 3.69 times for SBI. It indicates that there is no

operating profit influences the Working Capital performance.

On other hand HDFC, correlation coefficient 0.84, relationship strength is 0.697, adjusted R square 0.596 and standard error is 1.182. In overall result 69.7 percent of Operating Profit, which is influences the Working Capital performance.

TABLE 10.2 - Summary ANOVA Between Working Capital and Operating Profit

		SBI					HDFC				
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.014	1	.014	.001	.977	9.632	1	9.632	6.896	.079
	Residual	40.899	3	13.633			4.190	3	1.397		
	Total	40.913	4				13.823	4			

Critical value at 5% Level of Significance is 10.13

Source: Computed

It can be seen from the above Table No.10.2, overall dependence of Working Capital on Operating Profit of SBI and HDFC. By comparing F- values with F- critical value of both the banks, it is observed that null hypothesis

accepted for SBI and HDFC. Further it is concluded that there is no impact of operating profit on working capital performance of SBI and HDFC.

TABLE 10.3 - Summary Coefficients Between Working Capital and Operating Profit

		SBI					HDFC				
Model		Unstandardize d Coefficients		Standardize d Coefficients	t	Sig.	Unstandardize d Coefficients		Standardize d Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta			B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	74.92	132.92		.564	.612	-8.070	31.090		.260	.812
	Operating Profit	-.055	1.718	-.018	.032	.977	1.069	.407	.835	2.62	.079

Source: Computed.

It can be observed from Table-10.3 indicates Regression unstandardized and standardized coefficients, standard error and standardized betas of Working Capital and its profitability of SBI and HDFC. It can be seen that operating profit is negative co-efficient relation and positive beta with SBI and positive co-efficient relationship and positive beta with HDFC. It is indicated that there

is relationship exists for both the banks. Further, it is concluded that profitability (Operating Profit) has explained the Working Capital Performance of both the banks.

H4: There is no significance relationship between Working Capital and Return on Capital Employed.

Table 11.1- Model Summary Between Working Capital and Return on Capital Employed

		SBI				HDFC			
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	
1	.226	.051	-.265	3.59700	.834	.696	.595	1.18356	

Source: Computed

It can be seen from the above Table No.11.1, overall dependence of Working Capital on Return

on Capital Employed of SBI and HDFC. The correlation coefficient between WCR and ROCE

is 0.226, relationship strength is 0.051, and adjusted R square -0.265 and its standard error is 3.59 times for SBI. It indicates that 5.1 percent of profitability of return on capital employed influences the Working Capital performance.

On other hand HDFC, correlation coefficient 0.83, relationship strength is 0.696, adjusted R square 0.595 and standard error is 1.183. In overall result 69.6 percent of return on capital employed, which is influences the Working Capital performance

TABLE 11.2 - Summary ANOVA Between Working Capital and Return on Capital Employed

		SBI					HDFC				
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2.098	1	2.098	.162	.714	9.620	1	9.620	6.868	.079
	Residual	38.815	3	12.938			4.202	3	1.401		
	Total	40.913	4				13.823	4			

Critical value at 5% Level of Significance is 10.13

Source: Computed

It can be seen from the above Table No.11.2, overall dependence of Working Capital on return on capital employed of SBI and HDFC. By comparing F- values with F- critical value of both the banks, it is observed that null hypothesis

accepted for SBI and HDFC. Further it is concluded that there is no impact of return on capital employed on working capital performance of SBI and HDFC.

TABLE 11.3 - Summary Coefficients Between Working Capital and Return on Capital Employed

		SBI				HDFC					
Model		Unstandardize d Coefficients		Standardize d Coefficients	t	Sig.	Unstandardize d Coefficients		Standardize d Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta			B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	64.21	16.143		3.97	.028	31.28	16.142		1.93	.148
	ROCE	3.451	8.571	.226	.403	.714	13.61	5.194	.834	2.62	.079

Source:

It can be observed from Table-11.3 indicates Regression unstandardized and standardized coefficients, standard error and standardized betas of Working Capital and its profitability of SBI and HDFC. It can be seen that return on capital employed is positive co-efficient relation and positive beta with both SBI and HDFC. It is

Source: Computed

Computed

indicated that there is relationship exists for both the banks. Further, it is concluded that profitability (return on capital employed) has explained the Working Capital Performance of both the banks.

H5: There is no significance relationship between Working Capital and Return on Equity.

Table 12.1-Model Summary Between Working Capital and Return on Equity

Model	SBI				HDFC			
	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.755	.570	.427	2.42025	.563	.317	.089	1.77448

It can be seen from the above Table No.12.1, overall dependence of Working Capital on Return on Equity of SBI and HDFC. The correlation coefficient between WCR and ROE is 0.755, relationship strength is 0.570, and adjusted R square .427 and its standard error is 2.42 times for SBI. It indicates that 57 percent of profitability of

return on equity influences the Working Capital performance.

On other hand HDFC, correlation coefficient 0.567, relationship strength is 0.317, adjusted R square 0.089 and standard error is 1.774. In overall result 31.7 percent of return on equity, which is influences the Working Capital performance.

TABLE 12.2- Summary ANOVA Between Working Capital and Return on Equity

Model		SBI					HDFC				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	23.340	1	23.340	3.985	.140	4.376	1	4.376	1.390	.323
	Residual	17.573	3	5.858			9.446	3	3.149		
	Total	40.913	4				13.823	4			

Critical value at 5% Level of Significance is 10.13

Source: Computed

It can be seen from the above Table No.12.2, overall dependence of Working Capital on Return on Equity of SBI and HDFC. By comparing F-values with F- critical value of both the banks, it is

observed that null hypothesis accepted for SBI and HDFC. Further it is concluded that there is no impact of return on equity on working capital performance of SBI and HDFC.

TABLE 12.3 - Summary Coefficients Between Working Capital and Return on Equity

Model		SBI					HDFC				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta			B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	68.77	1.445		47.5	.00	86.29	10.829		7.96	.004
	ROE	.455	.228	.755	1.99	.140	-.789	.670	-.563	1.17	.323

Source: Computed.

It can be observed from Table-12.3 indicates Regression unstandardized and standardized coefficients, standard error and standardized betas of Working Capital and its profitability of SBI and HDFC. It can be seen that return on equity is

positive co-efficient relation and positive beta with SBI and negative co-efficient relationship and positive beta with HDFC. It is indicated that there is relationship exists for both the banks. Further, it is concluded that profitability (Return

on Equity) has explained the Working Capital Performance of both the banks.

H6: There is no significance relationship between Working Capital and Return on Earnings per Share.

It can be seen from the above Table No.13.1, overall dependence of Working Capital on

Earnings per Share of SBI and HDFC. The correlation coefficient between WCR and EPS is 0.566, relationship strength is 0.320, and adjusted R square .093 and its standard error is 3.05 times for SBI. It indicates that 9.3 percent of profitability of Earnings per Share influences the Working Capital performance.

Model	SBI				HDFC			
	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.566	.320	.093	3.04502	.884	.781	.708	1.00460

Source: Computed

On other hand HDFC, correlation coefficient 0.884, relationship strength is 0.781, adjusted R square 0.708 and standard error is 1.004. In

overall result 78.1 percent of earnings per share, which is influences the Working Capital performance.

Model		SBI					HDFC				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	13.097	1	13.097	1.412	.320	10.795	1	10.795	10.696	.047
	Residual	27.816	3	9.272			3.028	3	1.009		
	Total	40.913	4				13.823	4			

Critical value at 5% Level of Significance is 10.13

Source: Computed

It can be seen from the above Table No.13.2, overall dependence of Working Capital on Earnings per Share of SBI and HDFC. By comparing F- values with F- critical value of both the banks, it is observed that null hypothesis

accepted for SBI and HDFC. Further it is concluded that there is no impact of Earnings per Share on working capital performance of SBI and HDFC.

Model		SBI					HDFC				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta			B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	68.64	2.191		31.3	.000	67.429	1.928		34.9	.000
	EPS	.237	.199	.566	1.18	.320	.107	.033	.884	3.27	.047

Source: Computed.

It can be observed from Table-13.3 indicates Regression unstandardized and standardized coefficients, standard error and standardized betas of Working Capital and its profitability of SBI and HDFC. It can be seen that return on Earnings per Share is positive co-efficient relation and positive beta with both SBI and HDFC. It is indicated that there is relationship exists for both the banks. Further, it is concluded that profitability (EPS) has explained the Working Capital Performance of both the banks.

XI. FINDINGS

The findings of the study have been summarized below:

- ❖ It is observed that the working capital performance of HDFC was better than SBI during the study period.
- ❖ For Gross Profit performance HDFC is better, whereas risk and consistency point of view SBI is good.
- ❖ HDFC has high net profitability and lower risk than the SBI.
- ❖ It is found that the operating profit performance point of view SBI is better than the HDFC.
- ❖ HDFC is better performance with ROCE than SBI. It indicated that HDFC has high return on capital employed.
- ❖ It is observed that HDFC is good performance with ROE than SBI. It reflected that HDFC has high return on its equity.
- ❖ HDFC is efficient performance with EPS than SBI. Its impact on that HDFC has high returns shared to its shareholders.
- ❖ As per regression analysis, there is a partly impact of all profitability components on working capital performance of SBI.
- ❖ It is observed that regression analysis is revealed that Gross Profit, Net Profit and Earnings per Share components are very much influenced and remain components i.e. Operating Profit, Return on Capital

Employed and Return on Equity are partly influenced the Working Capital Performance of HDFC.

XII. SUGGESTIONS

- It is suggested that both banks must monitor their liquidity aspects and utilized current assets with planned manner.
- Receivables and payable management should be under control.
- It is suggested that adequate Working Capital management should be required to both banks; especially SBI should take care more.
- Balanced working capital should be planned as excessive working capital will give adverse impact on profitability and inadequate working capital should threaten the solvency of the banks.
- SBI has tremendous scope for improvement in optimized Working Capital for better profitability.

XIII. CONCLUSION

Working capital management plays significant role of finance management. Finance manager is essential to spend a great deal of time and maintaining optimal working capital for the running of the financial institutions. A lot funds now invested and received can be released for the alternate user. Ultimately liquidity and profitability of the financial institutions will be promoted. The problems under utilization of capacities of the banks will be solved to a larger extent with the improvement in the management of the working capital. A balanced approach should be followed by the banks to finance permanent current assets by long term sources and temporary current assets by short term sources of the finance.

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